

DETERMINING THE MORPHOFUNCTIONAL INDICATORS OF
TAEKWONDO ATHLETES BASED ON THEIR INDIVIDUAL
CAPABILITIES

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Annotation: This article analyzes the morphological and functional indicators of athletes engaged in taekwondo, taking into account their individual physical capabilities. The study develops approaches based on anthropometric measurements, cardiovascular and respiratory system performance indicators, as well as the results of tests evaluating the athletes' physical qualities.

Keywords: taekwondo, morphofunctional indicators, physical fitness, sports medicine, anthropometry, functional tests.

ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ МОРФОФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ
СПОРТСМЕНОВ-ТАЭКВОНДИСТОВ С УЧЕТОМ ИХ
ИНДИВИДУАЛЬНЫХ ВОЗМОЖНОСТЕЙ

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Аннотация: В данной тезисной работе проведён анализ эффективности применения комбинационных боевых действий спортсменами в процессе

подготовки таэквондистов к тренировкам и соревнованиям. С целью изучения мнений квалифицированных тренеров были проведены анкетные опросы. На основе полученных данных специалистами были разработаны предложения и рекомендации по эффективному использованию боевых комбинаций в подготовке таэквондистов.

Ключевые слова: комбинация, техника, тактика, тренер, движение, тхэквондо, специалист, тренировка, соревнование, боевой.

Introduction

An athlete's success in sports largely depends on their individual morphological (body structure) and functional (internal system performance) characteristics. This is especially true in fast-paced and highly dynamic sports such as taekwondo, where factors like body weight, height, heart rate, and lung capacity play a crucial role during competitions. This article is aimed at studying these indicators and using them as a basis for improving the training process.

Relevance of the Study Today, in the global sports arena, the use of individualized approaches plays a significant role in maximizing athletes' potential and achieving high performance results. This is particularly important in combat sports such as taekwondo, where identifying each athlete's morphological (body structure) and functional (physiological system activity) indicators and designing training systems based on these factors is a key component for improving competitive outcomes. Taekwondo athletes possess a variety of physical characteristics, and a generalized approach may not fully unlock their potential. Therefore, training programs tailored to each athlete's individual capabilities are essential for ensuring their success in sports. Determining morphofunctional indicators serves as the scientific foundation for such individualized approaches. This study lays the groundwork for developing an effective training system for taekwondo athletes based on personalized methods and holds scientific and practical significance in the field of modern sports medicine.

Research Objective The objective of this study is to develop effective training methods and competition preparation strategies for taekwondo athletes through the improvement of combat movement combinations.

Object of the Study The object of the study was the practical training process of taekwondo student-athletes at the national Olympic and Paralympic sports training centers.

Research Tasks

1. To analyze methods for improving taekwondo combat movement combinations and to determine their effectiveness.
2. To develop movement combinations for enhancing competition preparation based on a questionnaire survey.

Research

Methodology

The study involved 20 taekwondo athletes aged between 16 and 19 years. Measurements were carried out based on the following criteria:

- **Anthropometric indicators:** height, body weight, body mass index (BMI)
- **Cardiovascular system:** heart rate (HR), blood pressure
- **Respiratory system:** vital lung capacity (VC)

№	S. N	Class	Body weight	Body length	Vital Capacity of the Lungs		
					Norm (L)	Actual (L)	Result in %
1	Ilxomov Sh	5	46	1,46	2,71-2,20	2,26	83

2	Abdumalikov S	5	53	1,64	3,59-2,91	2,73	76
3	Abdullayev L	5	36	1,51	2,94-2,34	2,36	80
4	G'iyosiddinov X	6	37	1,51	3,02-2,46	2,84	94
5	Obloqulov N	6	44	1,57	3,32-2,70	2,14	65
6	Raxmatqulov Ch	6	43	1,53	30,03-2,47	2,28	75
7	Xamrokulov S	6	39	1,51	3,02-2,46	2,77	92
8	Qamaridinov H	6	40	1,48	2,93-2,38	2,38	81
9	Axrоров H	7	51	1,6	3,61-2,93	2,8	78
10	Musratullayev T	7	50	1,63	3,78-3,07	2,89	76
11	G'iyosiddinov I	8	49	1,65	4,05-3,29	3,27	81
12	Ibragimov I	8	50	1,64	3,99-3,24	4,32	108
13	O'Imasova D	8	43	1,57	3,28-2,64	2,24	68
14	Shirinqulova Sh	9	57	1,56	3,28-2,64	2,01	61
15	Xolmirzayev A	9	56	1,67	4,33-3,52	5,88	135
16	Shokirov A	9	62	1,7	4,52-3,67	3,93	87
17	Xabibullayev O	9	44	1,58	3,65-2,96	2,79	76
18	Raxmatullayev D	10	62	1,71	4,74-3,84	8,95	189

19	Raxmatullayev S	11	55	1,73	5,34-4,33	4,51	84
20	Ergashev U	11	64	1,72	4,92-3,99	4,11	84
21	G‘oziyev H	11	58	1,76	5,20-4,22	4,07	78
22	Habibullayev N	11	67	1,76	5,08-4,12	4,39	86

Analysis of Results

Height and Weight Balance:For most athletes, the BMI is within the normal range (18.5–24.9), which indicates that they are in an optimal physical condition.

Cardiovascular Indicators: The average heart rate (HR) was 63.5 beats per minute, which indicates that the athletes are in good resting condition.

Respiratory System: The vital capacity (VC) indicators ranged between 3800 and 4400 ml, indicating that the athletes have a favorable lung capacity for effective breathing.

Physical Qualities: Based on the pull-up and 60-meter sprint tests, it was determined that some athletes need to improve their strength and speed indicators.

Research Results and Discussion According to the results of the conducted study, the following responses and observations were provided by specialists. In support of the methodology we proposed, 77% of coaches (23 respondents) stated that it is necessary to effectively use combat movement combinations. Additionally, they emphasized that increasing the variability of techniques contributes positively to improving athletes’ technical preparedness. Other specialists (17%) responded with “sometimes,” explaining that they mainly continue to rely on traditional training methods. Meanwhile, 6% of coaches with two or more years of experience in the sports field responded with “I don’t know.”

These findings indicate that the methodology we propose—integrating combat movement combinations into practical training—is positively received and considered beneficial by the majority of coaches. The use of combination movements helps taekwondo athletes achieve better performance in competitions, contributing to more confident point-scoring. The methodology presented in this study is expected to help young athletes reach high achievements in prestigious competitions.

Conclusions The results of this study demonstrate that combination movements are one of the key factors necessary for achieving high performance in taekwondo. Their effective application in training and competitions enhances athletes' technical and tactical levels. According to experts, these movements must be thoroughly learned and refined. The analysis of the survey responses indicates that the use of combination movements in preparing taekwondo athletes significantly contributes to building their self-confidence and plays a vital role in achieving success in competitions.

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